

RESPONSES OF EGUSI MELON (*COLOCYNTHIS CITRULLUS L*) TO POULTRY MANURE IN OBUBRA, CROSS RIVER, SOUTH-SOUTH NIGERIA.

¹Agba, O.A, ²Adinya, I.B, ²Agbogo, E.A ²Oniah, M.A. Tiku, N. ¹Abam, ¹Prince and ¹Lifu, M.
¹Department of Agronomy, Cross River University of Technology Obubra, C.R.S
²Department of Agric. Economics and Extension, Cross River University of Technology, C.R.S.

ABSTRACT.

Field studies were conducted to determine the responses of Egusi Melon (*Colocynthis Citrullus L.*) to poultry droppings during the 2006 and 2007 cropping seasons in the teaching and Research farm, Faculty of Agriculture, Obubra, Cross River University of Technology, Cross River State, South-South Nigeria. The experiment has eight rates of well cured poultry droppings at 0.0, 2.0, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0, 12.0 and 14.0 tons/ha laid out in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications. The result showed that application of poultry droppings significantly improved the growth and yield of Egusi Melon. Poultry manure at 14.0 tons/ha recorded the highest vegetative growth. While 10.0 tons/ha of poultry manure produced the best seed yield of 1.26 and 1.25 ton/ha in 2006 and 2007 respectively.

KEYWORDS: Egusi Melon (*Colocynthis Citrullus L.*), Cucurbitaceae family, cropping seasons, Poultry manure.

INTRODUCTION

Egusi Melon (*Colocynthis Citrullus L.*) is a herbaceous annual vegetable with trailing hairy, ridge vine which bear tendrils and lobed leaves on long petioles that belong to the (Cucurbitaceae family (Okigbo, 1978, and Okoli 1984). The crop is an origin of Africa where it is cultivated in mixed cropping system with other crops like yams and cassava in peasant farms (Agba 2004 and Okigbo 1975).

The seed is rich in oils, proteins (most of which are essential amino acids) and minerals (Ogbonna and Obi 2007, Oyolu and Schippers 1982, Nwokolo and Sim 1987). The main harvested produce is the seed commonly consumed in Nigeria as a thickening for sauces and soups. It is also fry and eaten as snack. In traditional farming systems Egusi Melon canopy is use to control weed and run offs (soil erosion) is newly cultivated plots (Agba 2004)

Inspite of these economic importance, Egusi melon has not received much attention from scientific researchers. The production and out put (yield) of the crop is very low in the Obubra, central Cross River, South-South Nigeria. Ogbonna and Obi (2007) Observed that time of planting and soil nutrients are among the factors that significantly affect the growth and yield of Egusi melon. However, information on the nutritional requirement for increase growth and yield of the crop in South-South Nigeria are scantily. Agba (2004) recommended the combined use of 40kg/ha of phosphorus and nitrogen at 150kg/ha for the cultivation of Egusi in Obubra, central Cross River State.

This study aimed at investigating the rate of organic manure (poultry droppings) that will be require for optimum yield of Egusi melon seeds in Obubra, Cross River, South-South Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Field studies were conducted twice during 2006 and 2007 cropping seasons at the Teaching and Research farm of the Department of Agronomy, Obubra Campus, Cross River University of Technology, Obubra is located at longitude 08^o16 "E and Latitude 05^o58" N with mean annual rainfall of 2250-2500mm per annual (CRADP 1992). The mature seeds of Egusi melon was purchased from a peasant farmer at Ikom local government Area. Well cured poultry droppings were obtained from the livestock farm in the Department of Animal science, Obubra campus, Cross River University of technology.

2006 EXPERIMENT

The experimental Design was a Randomize complete Block Design (RCBD) with treatments that comprised

eight (8) rates of poultry droppings; 0.0, 2.0, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0, 12.0, and 14.0 tons/ha with each treatment replicated three times. The eight treatments were allocated completely at random to the eight plots in each Block using the table of Random numbers.

The Experiment site was cleared of existing vegetation, there after ploughed and divided into three blocks with each plot measuring 6x3m. Each plot was separated from adjoining plot by a space of one meter. The plots were tag with label of appropriate treatments for easy identification. Well cured poultry droppings were applied at the various rate stated above by broadcasting and completely work into the soil using garden fork at two weeks before planting the seeds. Egusi melon seeds were planted on 5th April, 2006/2007 cropping seasons at a of 1.0 x 0.7 meters between and within the rows respectively.

All cultural practices such as weed control, pest and diseases control were carried out as appropriate to keep the experimental site free from pests and diseases. The following agronomic parameters were recorded: numbers of leaves, braches per plant, and length of longest vine at 30 days after planting (D A P), days to first and 50 % flowering, fruiting, numbers of fruits (pods) plant, seed yield per plot and hectare respectively.

2007 EXPERIMENT.

The 2007 experiment was carried out using the same procedures as stated in 2006 experiment above

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data collected were subjected to Analysis of variance (ANOVA) procedure described by Steel and Torrie (1980) for randomized complete Block Design experiment. Separation of treatment means for statistical significant was done using the F-LSD procedures according to Obi (2001). The F-LSD test was done at 5% probability level.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result showed that application of poultry droppings significantly increased the growth of Egusi melon (*Colocynthis Citrillus L.*) (Table 1). All vegetative attributes measured (number of leaves, branches and length of longest vine) increased significantly with increases in the rate of poultry droppings used. However, numbers of branches per plant do not showed any significance differences increase beyond the poultry droppings of 10.0 tons/ha. The application of 14.0 tons/ha of poultry droppings gave the highest vegetative growth throughout the 2006 and 2007 cropping seasons.

These results agree with the findings of Ogbonna and Obi 2007 who reported improved vegetative attributes of Egusi melon influenced by poultry manure.

It was observed that all cases of treatment with poultry dropping enhance better flowering in Egusi melon as compare to untreated ones. Plots that received 8.0 tons/ha of poultry droppings produce earlier flowers than others that received higher or lower rates of poultry manure. The same rate prove better in reducing the days to 50% flowering, first and 50% fruiting of the crop in 2006 and 2007 cropping seasons. Ibrahim, *et al.*, (2001), Ogbonna and Obi (2007) recorded earlier flowering and better fruiting in melons as influenced by organic manure. The responses of Egusi melon to poultry droppings in 2007 follows the same trend as their effect on flowering and fruiting in 2006 cropping season (Table 3).

Crop yield significantly improved with successive increase in poultry dropping rates Table (2 & 3). However, increment in fruit and seed yield per plant and per hectare do not exceed the poultry rate of 12.0 tons/ha in both 2006 and 2007 cropping seasons. The weight 1,000 seeds were best (145.41 and 146.45 grams) in 2006 and 2007 cropping seasons respectively. The poultry rate of 10.0 ton/ha per hectare produced higher seed yield of 1.26 and 1.25 tons/ha that were better than all the other rates of poultry dropping in the two cropping seasons. Fokorede (2003) obtained similar result when he reported that the use of poultry manure improved soil chemical properties thereby enhancing high crop growth and yield.

REFERENCES.

Agba, O.A (2004). Effect of Nitrogen and Phosphorus on the growth and yield of Egusi (*Colocynthis Citrillus L.*) in Cross River State. Journal of Agriulture, Forestry and the social Science (JOAFSS). Vol.2. No.2: 1-7.

Cross River Agricultural Development Project (1992). Report on Wetlands of Cross River State. Nigeria 115 pp.

Fokorede, M.A B. (2003). Responses of Melons to planting dates and organic manure in tropical rainforest location. Expt. Agric. 23:20-30.

Ibrahim, R., Mahamad, M Tonniu, B., and Babaji, A (2001). Effect of organic manure on the growth and yield of cucurbits (water melon). Horticultural Science of Nigeria. 7.38-43.

Nwoko, E and Sim, J.S. (1987). Nutritional Assessment of defaulted pumpkin (*Telfaria occidentalis* Hook) by chick assay. Journal Science de Agric. 38:237- 246:

Obi, I.U (2001). Introduction to factorial Experiments for Agricultural, Biological and Social Science Research (2nd edition) Optimal International Ltd. Nigeria 92pp.

Ogabnna, P.E and Obi, I. U (2007). Effect of time of planting and poultry manure application on growth and yield of Egusi melon (*Colocynthis Citrullus L.*) in a derived Savannah. Agro-Ecology. Journal of Agriculture, Food, Environment and Extension Vol.6 Number 2.pp.33-38.

Okigbo, B.N (1978). Neglected plants of horticultural and nutritional importance in traditional farming systems of tropical Africa. Acta Hort. 53:13 1-150.

Okoli, B.E (1984). Wild and cultivated cucurbits in Nigeria. Econ. 38(3):350-357- edn) McGraw- Hill Book Company Inc. NY 633 pp.

Oyolu, C. and Schippers N. (1982). A study of the oil and the soluble protein components of five Egusi (*Colocynthis Citrillus L.*) cultivars. Trop. Sci. 24 (2) (92-98).

Schippers, R. (1997). African Idigenous vegetables. Workshop proceedings Jan 13-18, Limbe Cameroon ODA/iPGR/NRI. P.137-147.

Steel, R.G.D and Torrie, J.H. (1980). Principles and produces of statistics. A Biometrical approach second EditionMc. Grew Inc. New York. 63pp.

Received for Publication: 18/09/2009

Accepted for Publication: 24/12/2009

Corresponding Author:

Agba, O.A,

Department of Agronomy, Cross River University of Technology Obubra, C.R.S

Table 2. Effects of poultry droppings on the yield of Egusi Melon during 2007 cropping seasons. season.

Treats. poultry droppings Rate (t/ha).	Flower Attributes				No. of fruits per plant.	Yield Attributes		
	Days to first flowering	Days to 50% flowering	Days to first fruiting	Days to 50% fruiting		Fruit wt per plant (kg)	Seed wt per plant (g)	Seed wt per Hectare (t/ha)
0.0	39.8	47.5	62.3	90.4	4.2	113.65	46.21	0.65
2.0	36.6	45.3	57.1	84.6	6.3	135.81	51.34	0.76
4.0	34.3	43.1	54.3	78.3	8.1	143.69	58.13	0.85
6.0	31.3	42.0	50.5	72.1	9.2	200.43	69.52	0.98
8.0	28.5	37.5	48.4	69.3	10.3	234.71	75.64	1.03
10.0	33.7	37.4	45.2	67.1	12.5	334.85	100.32	1.25
12.0	38.5	40.3	41.1	70.2	10.5	352.33	54.32	1.15
14.0	41.6	38.2	41.3	70.4	8.5	211.56	73.55	1.14
F.LSD	2.1	1.1	3.0	3.2	0.01	5.31	4.2	0.02
P=0.05								

Table 1. Effects of poultry droppings on the vegetative growth of Egusi melon during 2006 and 2007 cropping seasons. 2

2006 Vegetative Growth Attributes					2007 Vegetative Growth Attributes			
Treats. Poultry Droppings Rate (ton/ha)	No. of leaves per plant 30DAP	No. of Branches per plant 30 DAP	Length of longest vine at 30 DAP(cm)	Vine diameter at 30 DAP (mm)	No. of leaves per plant 30 DAP	No. of Branches per plant 30 DAP	Length of longest vine 30 DAP (cm)	Vine diameter 30 DAP (mm)
0.0	11.1	3.1	78.3	3.5	11.3	3.2	79.2	3.3
2.0	13.1	4.3	95.2	4.7	13.7	4.4	96.1	4.8
4.0	13.5	4.5	113.5	4.9	14.1	4.6	113.7	5.3
6.0	15.2	5.1	121.3	5.1	15.3	5.1	123.1	5.7
8.0	16.5	5.5	129.7	5.6	16.1	5.3	129.1	6.6
10.0	17.5	6.1	133.5	6.7	17.4	6.2	134.5	6.8
12.0	17.5	6.1	141.7	10.2	17.7	6.2	140.9	10.1
14.0	21.4	6.1	152.4	11.1	20.6	8.2	163.5	10.3
F.LSD	1.11	0.01	12.3	0.02	1.01	0.01	3.4	0.02
P=0.05								

Table 3. Effects of poultry droppings on the yield of Egusi Melon during 2006 cropping seasons. season.

Treats. Poultry droppings Rate (t/ha).	Flower Attributes				No. of fruits per plant.	Yield Attributes			
	Days to first flowering	Days to 50% flowering	Days to first fruiting	Days to 50% fruiting		Fruit wt per plant (kg)	Seed wt per plant (g)	Seed wt per Hectare (t/ha)	1000 seed wt (g)
0.0	40.3	48.5	63.4	91.5	4.1	115.74	47.09	0.64	84.26
2.0	37.5	46.3	58.1	85.2	6.4	136.82	52.31	0.75	101.23
4.0	34.6	44.2	54.2	78.5	8.2	146.56	57.15	0.87	111.44
6.0	31.5	43.1	51.4	73.3	9.3	205.51	68.74	0.99	116.32
8.0	29.1	38.4	49.3	68.4	10.1	236.72	74.644	1.04	122.72
10.0	34.6	37.4	46.2	67.1	12.7	335.54	101.34	1.26	146.45
12.0	38.7	40.5	42.3	70.3	11.0	260.21	85.35	1.16	122.15
14.0	41.6	38.2	41.2	70.1	8.5	213.57	74.46	1.13	113.89
F.LSD P=0.05	2.1	1.1	2.0	3.2	0.01	5.31	4.2	0.002	11.53